

Politics of Personal Naming and Islamization: A Sociological Study of the Naming Patterns among the Dudekula Community

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Abstract

Naming practices are complex in nature and are often linked with various macro and micro levels of religious, cultural, and political factors. They come with many life stories and sentiments attached to them. Furthermore, naming can have political-ideological undertones, often serving as an assertion against structures of domination. Names also serve a purpose beyond being mere labels for individuals. They transcend these functional roles, suggesting that different processes that go into naming. In this background, this paper seeks to comprehend the processes of Islamization within the Dudekula community in South India through the lens of personal names and naming practices. Firstly, it examines how naming practices reflect the community's accommodation of Islamization while maintaining traditional syncretic beliefs of Hindu origin. Secondly, it explores the strategies and methods of accommodation employed by the Dudekula community to navigate the tension between their traditional cultural beliefs and the increasing influence of Islamization on naming practices. Finally, it investigates identity negotiation and the interplay of identities, particularly through the phenomenon of temporarily adopting Muslim names during critical social events, such as marriages. By analyzing these practices, the paper aims to shed light on how the Dudekula community balances their dual religious and cultural identities in the face of evolving socio-religious influences.

Keywords

Islamization, Dudekulas, syncretic practices, naming

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Introduction

The diverse functions of naming have been extensively discussed and described as the means of identifying people, their gender, caste, family affiliations, and religion (Rytnes, 1999; Finch, 2008; Rahman, 2013; Pilcher, 2015; Askuri and Kuipers, 2018; Ahmad et al., 2023). However, names serve a purpose beyond mere labels for individuals and transcend these functional roles, indicating different processes that go into naming, reflecting a specific era's sociocultural and religious characteristics (Rahman, 2013). Names come with many life stories and sentiments attached to them and can have political-ideological undertones, often as an assertion against the structures of domination. Names play a major role in constructing social identities; thus naming is political. Historically, some people have changed their names as part of the resistance, and some have stressed their names as part of the assertion. Cassius Clay changed his name to Muhammad Ali after winning the heavyweight championship as a political statement and resistance to slavery. Similarly, Malcolm-X removed Little, his enslaver's name, kept X, and later embraced Islam (Finch, 2008). As a sign of his association with Islam, Malcolm X added Shabaaz to his name, and finally, he renamed himself El-Hajj Malik El-Shabaaz (Rytnes, 1999). Nelson Mandela, in his autobiography, mentions that on his first day of school, his teacher added an English name, Nelson, to his name and, hereafter, they would be called with English names in the school (Mandela, 2008). This reflects the impact of British colonization and cultural imposition on education in African communities.

Names also help in understanding sociocultural changes over a period of time. For example, my name is *Nyamath Hussain*, *Nyamath* means blessing. Certain sections among Sunni Muslims (like Tablighi Jamat) do not advocate such naming in isolation. They call for an addition to this name. So, for them, *Nyamatullah* should have been my name as it means the blessing of Allah (giving the name a complete meaning). The Suffix in my name, *Hussain*, gives out a perception that I belong to the Shia sect of Islam. I realized this Sunni-Shia difference in names when one of my Mappila Muslim friends enquired and explained its meaning during the course of my PhD studies. This revealed to me a new dimension of how people of different sectoral practitioners perceive or give meaning to a name that is not theirs. In the place where I belong, my name does not serve as a marker of any sect; however, Mappila Muslims or Tablighis perceive this as Shiite. For my grandparents and parents, this was just an imitation practice that showed a subjective understanding of naming culture. Firstly, there is a high respect for Shias among Muslims, as they were the ruling class in this region. The common masses tried to imitate Shias so that they could claim respect in society, and it is also believed that Shia rulers of Golconda used to give preference to people with a Shia name (Naqvī & Rao, 2004). Secondly, Dargah practices in my home, which we followed before Tablighi Jamaat's entry into our region, played a significant role. Lastly, the assumption that lengthy names carry high respect resulted in a trend of lengthy names. Names, therefore, are not just identifiers with practical intent but are laden with historical, cultural, and political significance.

As part of my PhD, I conducted ethnographic fieldwork between November 2022 and January 2024 in a village in the Rayalaseema region of Andhra Pradesh, predominantly inhabited by the Dudekulas, an artisan community of Hindu origin. They were traditionally in cotton cleaning and mattress-making activity and embraced Islam during the 13th century

with the spread of Islam in the Deccan region under the influence of Sufi saints (Thurston and Rangachari, 1909; Saheb, 2003). Renowned for their syncretic beliefs, the Dudekulas retained many Hindu convictions and practices despite their conversion to Islam (Mohammad, 2016). This retention of Hindu beliefs is primarily due to their cultural contact with former co-religionists and the lack of interest and involvement on the part of Sufis to assimilate them into mainstream Islam. Sufi teachings give individual spiritual emancipation primacy without any intermediaries between the saint and devotee, which resulted in a paucity of textual Islamic practices among the Dudekulas. Consequently, their naming patterns reflect a blend of Hindu and Islamic influences, underscoring their unique cultural identity.

Against this background, the study is structured into three main parts. The first section delves into the politics of naming among Muslims, providing a brief history of the Dudekula community. After outlining the objectives of the inquiry, the paper proceeds to detail the methods employed for collecting empirical data. This is followed by an analysis of how names serve as intricate markers of religion and culture and how these markers are negotiated within context-specific scenarios. The focus is particularly on the Dudekula community, which adheres to syncretic beliefs and seeks to balance both Islamic and Hindu customs, all within a period marked by competing religious identities. This exploration sheds light on how such a community navigates its cultural and religious identity through the complex practices of naming.

1. Conceptual Framework

The current work draws on Tariq Rahman (2013, 2016) and Askuri and Joel C. Kuipers (2017, 2018, 2019), who analyzed personal names for a systematic understanding of Islamization² in Pakistan and Indonesia, respectively, and adapted their studies to the Indian context.

Rahman (2013, 2016) argues that personal names serve as indicators of religious (including sectarian) identity and reflect changes in identity construction. His studies explore the relationship between Islamic identity and personal names in Pakistan, emphasizing the larger impact of standardized names on minority sects and religions and the decline of cross-sectarian name usage. On investigating how personal names signal religious identities, Rahman highlights the frequency of Islamic components in names as an index of religiosity and sect type. He explores how names may be changed to signal a desire for a new religious identity, suggesting that the Islamization and Arabization of personal names in Pakistan may indicate changes in identity construction. This shift points towards a more religiously homogenized society as personal names evolved in response to the changing socio-political landscape in the post-Zia ul Haq period (1977-88). He found that the Islamic component in names has increased along with ‘meaningful Islamic names’ from the 1950s to 2010s; slightly higher among the urban middle-class people than among rural people. He also provides historical context for the evolution of naming practices,

² For the purpose of this study, Islamization is defined as a growing awareness of ‘Islamic consciousness’ (for more details, refer to Rahaman (2013)).

including the impact of colonialism and the socio-political changes in South Asia in general and Pakistan in particular, and offers a comprehensive analysis of how names function as markers of identity and agents of change in a dynamic cultural setting.

Askuri and Kuipers (2017, 2018, 2019) examined the change in naming preferences in Java due to the commitment to normative Islam from 1965 onwards with the beginning of Suharto's regime. This commitment further intensified with the revival of Islamic *dakwah* (proselytization) in the 1980s. Their research underscores Indonesia's historical engagement with external cultures and religions, challenging simplistic narratives of Arabization or Westernization. By using personal names as a lens to understand broader social changes, their studies suggest that naming practices can reflect shifts in religious piety and cultural affiliations. The cultural and social dynamics that influenced naming practices in Java included state policies, such as compulsory Islamic education of two hours a week in schools post-1965 and establishing schools in remotest areas with the introduction of a six-year compulsory education in 1950. Their works discuss a significant shift in naming traditions among Javanese Muslims, with a move towards Arabic names that reflect the aspirations of parents to connect their children with larger Islamic societies. Their research highlights the blend of local and Arabic influences and identifies three key patterns in the Arabization of Javanese names: *purification*, where standardized Arabic-Indonesian transliteration is used; *hybridization*, where a blend of Arabic and Javanese names occurs; and *super hybridization*, where Arabic names coexist with Indonesian and European names. The prevalence of super hybrid names has grown rapidly, particularly since the 2000s, due to increased integration and communication with the global economy. Their research also captures the tension between Islamization and cultural identity in Southeast Asia, Indonesia in particular and underscores the struggle between maintaining local beliefs and the unifying force of Islam.

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Rahman, as well as Askuri and Kuipers describe the growing tendency of Islamization through the Arabization of names in their works. However, they do not consider the question of agency, whether individual or collective, regarding the changes in the practices of naming they identify. They do not pay much attention to the effects of syncretic or already existing traditional practices. Therefore, this paper seeks to comprehend the processes of Islamization within the Dudekula community in South India. Secondly, in the context of personal names, this paper focuses on strategies followed by members of the Dudekula community to understand how individuals navigate the tension between their traditional syncretic cultural beliefs and the increasing influence of Islamization on naming practices. Thirdly, it explores the negotiation and interplay of identities through a phenomenon of temporarily changing to Muslim names during critical social events like marriages in the Dudekula community.

2. Methodology

In my fieldwork, I collected the names of all Dudekula community members living in the village of Gundreddy Palle; altogether, 637 inhabitants. The data is broken down into their gender, marital status, paternal home places, and religious orientation, with the

help of a Household Survey I carried out between 2022 November and 2024 January. Additionally, I gathered the names of the participants’ forefathers to understand naming practices over time. I categorized the birth years of the participants across the last seven decades to comprehend the broader implications of macro socio-cultural developments in India, such as the Babri mosque demolition in 1990, riots and pogroms against Muslims (Kausar, 2006), and micro socio-cultural developments in the village, such as the building of a new mosque in 2012 and the appointment of a full-time Islamic preacher in 2014.

Based on the situation and the respondent’s willingness to provide data, I collected most of the narratives for my research during the Household Survey, which commenced after six months of my stay in the field. Some of the information came to light through casual chit-chats, whether in one-on-one or group settings or simply through observation. Drawing from this pool of knowledge and the rapport I had developed with the respondents, I conducted unstructured interviews in the local language, Telugu, as most of the respondents were only fluent in Telugu and felt more comfortable communicating in it. These interviews allowed me to further explore the sentiments attached to their names. Many of the narratives have been used in this article to identify key themes and support the arguments presented.

In addition, I collected details about the household deities of Dudekula residents to explore the intersectionality of changes in naming patterns. As this study focuses on the naming patterns of the Dudekula community in Gundreddy Palle, I excluded the names of daughters-in-law, husbands in matrilocal residence (*illarikam alludu*), and first-generation migrants because their parental homes are outside the village. Moreover, I took precautions to avoid duplicating the names of women who married within the village.

My aim now is limited to understanding the sentiments attached to the cultural, religious, and political connotations of the participants’ full names, which should not be confused with nicknames. Nicknaming is more informal and flexible. Using nicknames can be a sign of affection, closeness, or familiarity (Pilcher, 2015) Additionally, nicknames are used to abuse the person with their physical characteristics (Palsson, 2014). Observing the naming pattern could be a limited attempt to understand the totality of the functioning of religion. However, names are a powerful marker in understanding the nexus of religion and region, and they are, in turn, linked with social history. Name-changing becomes critical during marriage and death (Mocherla, 2020). For my research, it is important to keep in mind that in the present Indian context, a Priest, Qazi, or Pastor performs the marriage ritual, preferably using the names of the bride and groom reflecting their religion. Dalits who convert to Islam or Christianity face this issue as they carry the names of their ancestors.

3. ‘Other names’: *Māru-pērlu*

When I first came to Gundreddy Palle, my field site, I found difficulty in accessing the respondents. In order to make entry into the field, I first spoke with the headmaster of the Primary School, where I encountered a Telugu term, *māru-pērlu* (other names). He gave me some initial insights into the village’s practices. He said that many Dudekula students possess two names; one is Hindu, and the other is Muslim. He also introduced me to

a student whose registered name is Narasimhulu (the name of a Hindu god), but students in the school called him Rafi (a Muslim name). For convenience, they choose either a Muslim or Hindu name for records purposes. Later, when I spoke with Muhammad³ (a male in his mid-40s), a red chili merchant, he told me that his registered name is Chinnanna (a Telugu name which means ‘younger brother’); his school teacher suggested that name when he joined the school because having a Muslim name may create problems in availing the reservation benefits provided by the state. However, the rules are completely different, and the lack of knowledge among government officials about the rules also creates problems for Dudekulas.

When his son Dastagiri (a male in his mid-20s), a software engineer working in a metropolitan city, was blessed with a baby boy, they consulted a Hindu priest for the first letter in the child’s name. Based on the position of the stars (*Bharani nakshatra 2nd Padam*) and the Lunar date (it happened to be *Purnima*, full moon), the priest suggested a name starting with the letter L- Li, Lu, Lea, or Lo. In addition to this, the priest asked the parents to perform Rudrabhishekam, a Hindu ritual dedicated to Lord Shiva. Dastagiri wanted a Muslim/ Islamic name for his boy, and considering the priest’s recommendation, with the assistance of the internet, the child’s family named the baby Liyan, an Arabic word that means ‘cute’. However, Muhammad named his second child Brahmam in memory of their (Hindu) household deity, Potuluri Veera Brahmam, because he believed that the deity blessed his family with the second child and ended their wait of 15 years. Thus, the complexity of naming practices in my field intrigued and pushed me to observe the names in general and ‘*other names*’ in particular in the village.

In my empirical observation, Dudekulas use Islamic names, Hindu names, or a mix of Islamic and Hindu names. What is unique here is that the naming practices are flexible. At birth, they have Hindu gods’ and godmen’s names, such as Obulesu, Narasimha, Potuluri Brahmam, Ranga swamy, and Govindu for boys and goddesses’ and god women’s names, such as Lakshmi, Sunkulamma, Eshwari, but after some point, they start using Islamic names. This may happen vice versa. Shift in the naming practices does not guarantee continuation of the same in the next generations. This practice is made challenging when it comes to choosing matrimonial alliances. Typically, the Dudekulas with Islamic names prefer to marry other similar Dudekulas with Islamic names. The same is the case of Dudekulas with Hindu names and those with Christian names⁴. However, we can trace a distinctive pattern in a few cases where class and cultural practices cut across these naming conventions in matrimonial alliances.

4. Social Manifestation of Names

In India, as part of anti-Hindi imposition agitation and de-Sanskritization of the Tamil language from 1937 onwards (Ranjan, 2021), Tamils started using non-Sanskrit, non-

³ Interestingly, everyone calls Muhammad as Mammud, including himself. When I addressed him as Muhammad in a group conversation, others told me that there is no Muhammad in this village.

⁴ In Andhra Pradesh, while Dalits make up the majority of Christians, people from various castes also follow Christianity. In my field village, members of eight households (though not all family members) attend Sunday mass in a nearby village. However, Christianity is not visibly reflected in their everyday lifestyle, with only one child in the entire village bearing a Christian name.

Brahmin, or secular names like *Tamilisai* (Tamil music) and *Annadorai* (elder brother). After visiting Russia in 1932, EV Ramaswamy Naiker, popularly known as Periyar, an anti-caste, anti-religion, social reformer of South India, named the daughters of a Dravidian intellectual as Russia and Moscow. By doing so, he had given a new kind of orientation to naming culture. With the rise of communism in South India, names like Stalin, Marx, and Lenin came into use (Venkatachalapathy, 2017). Subaltern communities started using words like *Vanakkam aiya*, which means ‘regards sir’, as a name given to be called respectfully. The Dalits also used this kind of approach in the Telugu region. They started adding words like *Ayya* (father or sir), *Anna* (elder brother), *Akka* (elder sister), and *Amma* (mother) to have respectable names. For example, Peddigadu became Peddanna, or Subbigadu became Subbanna. Another kind of approach is naming their kids after the local gods and goddesses because the upper caste does not dare to disrespect the gods. Names like Subbarayudu, Rangaswamy, Nagaraju, Venkateshwarlu, Lakshmi, and Saraswathi came into use. G Kalyan Rao’s *Antarani Vasantham* (Untouchable Spring) novel mentions that Dalits started adopting the names of Hindu gods and Goddesses from street plays (Sarveswar, 2021).

Bhagya Reddy Varma (1888-1939), born into the Mala caste as Madari Bhagayya, was one of the early Dalits who recognized the importance of names in the Telugu region. He was a social reformer and activist in Hyderabad state who worked for the downtrodden before Ambedkar. For his efforts, he is known as the “Father of the Dalit movement in Andhra Pradesh”. He rejected the Pancham identity to Dalits, called them Adi-Hindus, and started the Adi-Hindu movement. The word Adi-Hindu means original inhabitants of India. He started social and cultural movements to create an equitable space for the Dalits. He took the name ‘Bhagya Reddy Varma’ to claim a higher status in the society. Reddy and Varma are higher caste names; the former one is forward dominant non-brahmin, and the latter one is Brahmin (Gundimeda, 2013).

On the other hand, names can also be used as a part of assertion or self-respect. Madigas, one of the Scheduled Castes of Telugu regions with the Dandora movement, started using their caste names as a suffix. This movement was led by Manda Krishna and Ponugoti Krupakar. The Dandora movement invented a dignified meaning for the term “Madiga,” which was regarded as an abusive phrase and has publicized its historical significance (Ratnam, 2008). The Dandora movement, which was started with the aim of sub-categorization of scheduled castes, has achieved immeasurable success on the social front, especially concerning the Madiga identity and self-respect. A term associated with filthiness became a symbol of identity and self-respect ever since Manda Krishna and others of the Dandora movement began to attach it to their names just like forward castes like Reddy, Rao, and Chaudhury (Purushotham, 2010). Though it dates to Kanshiram times (1980s), Chamars of Uttar Pradesh, under the dynamic leadership of Chandrashekhar Azad, vividly use the suffix Chamar like Madigas of Telugu states.

Rajnikant Parmar (2020) explored the phenomenon of changing surnames among Dalits in urban areas of Gujarat to get away from discrimination in residential spaces, education institutions, and the job market. Dalit surnames are attached with stereotypes by caste Hindus; so, to escape this discrimination in urban spaces, Dalits started using Other Backward Classes (OBC) surnames or ambiguous surnames, which are used in multiple caste categories. This strategy may backfire and attract double discrimination within and

outside the caste. For instance, Parmar (2020) argues that if the savarnas (upper caste people) come to know about this at educational institutions, workplaces, or residential places, it will adversely affect the Dalit person. Dalits who are engaged in activism and their relatives who did not change their surnames may not continue the social relations with them. Moreover, this act of changing surnames may impact the reservation benefits provided by the State and create difficulty in finding matrimonial alliances.

In recent times, two bureaucrats, Gandham Chandrudu and Praveen Kumar, have played an essential role in creating a respectable and new identity for Dalit residential spaces and students in the Telugu region, respectively (Aiyappa, 2020; Rao, 2021; Teja, 2021). Gandham Chandrudu, when he was working as a District collector for Anantapur between December 2019 and June 2021, started renaming Scheduled Castes habitats with the names of freedom fighters and social reformers such as Ambedkar, Gandhi, Nehru, Netaji, and Ferrer⁵ (Aiyappa, 2020). When he was working as Secretary for Telangana Social Welfare Residential Education Institution Society between 2013 and 2021, Praveen Kumar came up with the acronym SWAEROS⁶ for all current and past students. This action helped form a network of students and gave Dalit students who had “derogatory” surnames a respectable identity. This act also helped build morale and self-confidence among students. It all first started with changing surnames on social media platforms and consequently in official records (Rao, 2021; Teja, 2021).

5. Dynamics of Naming among Dudekulas

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Before we enter into the dynamics of naming among Dudekulas of Gundreddy Palle, I must present the grammatical structure of personal names (See Table 1) to better understand the coming arguments.

Table 1. Grammatical structure of the names

Gender	Caste name	Kinship name	(Prefix) Actual name (Suffix)
Male	Dudekula	Badur gari	Pedda Husenayya
Male	Dudekula	Chanti gari	Nadipi Husenanna
Male	Dudekula	Saidanna gari	Chinna Husenayya
Male	Dudekula	Karrenna gari	Husenayya
Male	Dudekula	Pamayya gari	Husen
Female	Dudekula	Yerranna gari	Pedda Husenamma

⁵ Vicente Ferrer Moncho (9 April 1920 – 19 June 2009) was a Jesuit missionary from Spain who spent his life working to improve the lives of the poor in Anantapur by establishing the Rural Development Trust. Because of his charitable works, he is seen as an esteemed person in that region. Parents naming their children as Ferrer is also a common phenomenon out of respect for him.

⁶ The “SW” stands for state welfare and “AERO” in Greek means air and sky, indicating limitless possibility.

Gender	Caste name	Kinship name	(Prefix) Actual name (Suffix)
Female	Dudekula	Akkapalle	Nadipi Husenakka
Female	Dudekula	Solaveti	Chinna Husenamma
Female	Dudekula	Palutagi	Husenamma
Female	Dudekula	Naddi	Husen bi

Each Dudekula in the village has their caste name as a surname, followed by their kinship group name. However, many have recently stopped including kinship names because lengthy names create complications in government records. For instance, the Union Public Service Commission, the premier governmental body that recruits top bureaucratic positions, allows a maximum of 30 characters in a name in their application forms. As the final element comes a person’s actual name, which can be broken into three main parts: prefix, name, and suffix. Sometimes, the name part contains more than one word. The prefix indicates birth order, which can be counted separately for male and female children in the same family. For example, *Pedda* is for the eldest, *Nadipi* is for the middle, and *Chinna* is for the youngest. Similarly, gender can be tracked through suffixes: for males, they use *ayya* (father or sir), *anna* (elder brother), and for females, they use *amma* (mother), *akka* (elder sister).

5.1. Islamic names among Dudekulas

During the initial days of my fieldwork, I encountered a peculiar situation related to names. In the evenings, I would go to places where teens hang out. One day, I asked a guy named Sharif about another guy named Sharif, providing a physical description. He responded, “Did he say his name was Sharif? (*Vāḍi pēru śarīphā ēṅṅi?*) My name is Sharif; his name is Narasimhulu.” This reply puzzled me as I knew both of them as Sharif. So, in this section, I aim to explore different incidents involving four individuals named Sharif (whose registered name or “*Māru pēru*” is Sharif) to understand how they perceive their names. Each of these individuals embodies a unique relationship with their name, highlighting various dimensions of identity, legitimacy, and cultural significance attached to names within their community.

Firstly, there is Sharif, who is called that name by birth. This individual, born in a dudekula family, has been called the Muslim name Sharif since birth and has never been known by any other name. For him, the name Sharif is an intrinsic part of his identity, one that carries a sense of authenticity and continuity. He believes his name has more legitimacy because it has been unaltered and constant in his life. He even corrected me when I called him Narasimhulu during a conversation.

Secondly, we have Sharif by registration. I learned from other respondents that his birth name was Narasimhulu, but his parents changed it to Sharif at the time of school admissions. For him, the name Sharif holds official status and is legitimized by its presence in formal records. For the same reason, he will not mention his birth name to anyone. He feels that the act of registering his name as Sharif grants it a form of bureaucratic authenticity and aligns his identity with his chosen name in a formalized manner.

Thirdly, there is the individual who introduces himself as Sharif, although his birth name is Narasimhulu, and he has never been registered by that name. He believes he has earned the name Sharif through his regular attendance at the mosque and his adherence to Islamic practices. For him, being a “practicing Muslim” justifies his use of the name Sharif, and he views this religious and cultural commitment as a source of legitimacy for his chosen name.

Lastly, there is the person who claims to be that name (Sharif) occasionally. This person uses the name Sharif sporadically, drawing on a historical and familial connection. His forefathers had both their household deity’s name (Narasimha Swamy) and Sharif as their names, and he invokes this tradition to justify his occasional use of the name, though his birthname and the registered name are Narasimhulu, he claims as Sharif when he visits the mosque or has a conversation with Islamic reformist organizations. For him, the name Sharif is a link to his ancestry and cultural heritage, which he calls upon when he feels it is relevant or advantageous.

These differing perspectives on the name Sharif reveal the complex ways in which individuals navigate, negotiate and claim their identities in relation to their name. Here, we have four different ways in which naming practice is played out: name as an unchanging and inherent part of oneself, formal recognition (thereby seeking state legitimacy) of the name, claim changed as an effect of religious practices, and occasional choice of indexing connection through familial and historical ties. Each story reflects a unique interplay of personal, cultural, and institutional factors that shape how these individuals perceive and assert their identities through their names. However, all the elders who are inclined towards Hindu descent, especially from their kinship group, still call them Narasimhulu, disregarding their individual preferences that, in fact, reflect the shift to Islamization. Interestingly, these people who are going through the shifts also respond to them without stressing any differences of opinion.

5.2. Hindu names among Dudekulas

As mentioned earlier, Dudekulas follow a blend of Islamic and Hindu naming practices. However, the Dudekulas in Gundreddy Palle do not prefer hybrid names. Instead, they opt for one registered name and another unregistered name. In this section, with the help of narratives, an effort is made to explore the historical background and reasons behind their choice of Hindu names.

Husenamma, a 48-year-old daughter-in-law in the village, shared a story popularly known as the “tiger incident” regarding the prevalence of the names Narasimha or Lakshmi in their kinship group:

Three or four generations ago, when our forefathers were returning from Nandyal on bullock carts after their business, they saw a tiger (*Pedda Puli*) sleeping on the road in the Nallamalla ghat area near Sarva Narasimha Swamy temple. They prayed to Sarva Narasimha Swamy, saying they would name their next-generation children after him if they crossed the ghat safely. Suddenly, the tiger jumped up and ran away (*Egiri pōyindi*) as if someone had beaten him. From then onwards, we started naming

our kids after the deity, if a girl, ‘Lakshmi’ (Lachamma), and if a boy, ‘Narasimhulu’.
(Husenamma, a 48-year-old Dudekula widow)

When I asked her, “But in your home, the children’s names are not Narasimhulu,” she replied, “Nowadays, we give the name Narasimha Swamy name at birth; however, we change it later.”

The above narrative explains that giving a Hindu name at birth and changing the name to an Islamic name is a conscious choice to accommodate their age-old practice. Whereas in the below narrative, giving a Hindu god name is fulfilling a vow made to God in return for a child to infertile couples.

Peramma, a 75-year-old dudekula widow, shared a narrative regarding naming practices in their family. According to her:

Our younger son, Chinna Narasimhulu, and daughter-in-law, Usha Begum, did not conceive even after seven years of marriage. At that time, some of our relatives told us about a lady in Rangapuram village through whom Lord Shiva speaks. If anyone approaches her with their problems, she suggests things to do and then the problems go away. She told us to visit the Srisailam temple and make a vow to Shiva. We prayed and vowed that if a boy were born in our family, we would name him after Shiva.
(Peramma, a 75-year-old Dudekula widow)

Incidentally, soon they were blessed with a boy. They added the name of the household deity, Narasimha and named the child ‘Shiva Narasimha.’ In a similar instance, Narasimhulu (male, 52) and Perambi (female, 47), who did not conceive after 12 years of marriage, also visited the same lady and named their son and daughter after Lord Shiva: Shiva Narasimha (18) and Shiva Lakshmi (11), respectively. In both instances, the ceremony is first performed for their household deity and immediately after that for Lord Shiva. One day, while chit-chatting in a group, Shiva Narasimha (18) told me, ‘Brother, I am Shiva only in the village. People in Hyderabad or on social media (Instagram) know me as Althaf’ (*Anna! Ikkadē śiva; inṣṭāgrām lō, siṭī lō anta altāph ani telusu*).

Ranga Swamy’s (male, 17) case is a little peculiar. The shift in his name is from Sufi/Muslim to Hindu/local godman. His birth name was Kasim, but it was later changed to Ranga Swamy. He explained:

When I was a child, I had health issues. Doctors told my parents that I would not survive. When my parents named me Ranga Swamy, miraculously, I survived. After my name was changed, our fortunes turned for the better (*Pēru mārcina tarvātē kalisi vaccindi aṅṭā*). We even named our nursery after Ranga Swamy. (Rangaswamy, a 17-year-old male)

In their ancestral family tradition, they venerated Ranga Swamy, who was also the name of Ranga Swamy’s paternal grandfather, Rangayya. However, later generations started worshipping Jamal Nayana, a local Sufi saint. Despite this local collective shift, when

a series of unfortunate things happened in Ranga Swamy's family, they continued their tradition of venerating Ranga Swamy.

These narratives offer a glimpse into how a deity's name becomes ingrained within a family or kinship group, persisting across generations. For some, like Husenamma's family, the use of a Hindu household deity's name at birth remains symbolic, though still actively practiced. In other instances, aspirations for a child introduce new household deities into family traditions. In the case of Rangaswamy, his family reverted to worshipping their old deity, while his uncles adopted Sufi practices. What emerges from these narratives is a deeper understanding that people's primary concern is the fulfillment of their needs or the psychological comfort that provides them with hope. This hope is not confined by religious boundaries; as long as their needs are met, the specific religious or cultural context becomes secondary. Whether it's invoking the name of a household deity or embracing Sufi worship, these practices are not about rigid adherence to one faith but rather a flexible and pragmatic approach to spirituality that transcends religious lines.

However, what is crucial for us is the subjective meanings given by the Dudekulas of Gundreddy Palle in continuation of age-old traditional practices of naming, which prioritize Hindu household deity names in the times of Islamization of the community. These subjective meanings are important because they not only guard but secure and continue the syncretic practices in the community. When I asked elderly people what happens if they do not give names of Hindu gods and goddesses to children in their families, the responses were very similar and all related to the health of the baby. The most frequent answers were that the babies would not drink milk if they did not have those names. This phenomenon is not limited to Hindu gods alone; it can be observed in Sufi believers, too. For instance, in the case of Kashamma (female, 65), whose family worships a local Sufi saint, all the baby girls were named Adam Bi. A frequent explanation was that otherwise, the babies would fall ill. Peramma (female, 75) added, "Our children will go mad if we do not give them the name of Narasimha Swamy." When I inquired about this naming compulsion with Peram Bi (female, 35), a daughter-in-law in the village whose family has named all males Narasimhulu for the last three generations, she repeated the same belief with a sarcastic smile, glancing at her husband's brother, who is mentally ill. Though these two women responded with similar words, Peramma accepts that belief as a fact, while Peram Bi is not vocal about it but does not actually believe in it.

Another reason for changing names among kids is their initial response to the name. If the child does not respond positively to the given name, then parents may consider changing it. For example, in the case of Nazeera (female, 7), used to cry when she was called Ishita, her previous Hindu name.

5.3. Islamization of Names

When analyzing the data, I faced some problems with categorization, as presented in Table 2 below. I ended up with 600 names in my sample. I categorized the names into three groups: Telugu names, Urdu names, and Urdu names with Telugu prefixes or suffixes. Though Telugu names are synonyms with Hindu names, sometimes they contain non-religious aspects. In the case of Urdu names, though they are synonyms with Islam/

Muslim names (*turukolla perlu*), these naming practices do not follow Islamic scholarly debate as every Islamic sect provides their own logic on correct naming practices (for more, refer to Rahman, 2016). Additionally, I included Sufi names in Urdu/ Muslim names because my respondents perceived Sufi names as Islamic.

This categorization reflects the nuanced and complex ways in which names are chosen and used within the community. Telugu names often carry cultural and regional significance that extends beyond religious identification. They can index linguistic and familial traditions, reflecting the broader cultural heritage of the individuals. Urdu names, while often associated with Islamic identity, show a diversity that goes beyond strict religious connotations. The inclusion of Sufi names underlines the influence of Sufi traditions within the community, which are seen as integral to their Islamic identity despite varying from orthodox Islamic naming conventions. Urdu names with Telugu suffixes or prefixes represent a blend of cultural influences, highlighting the intersection of linguistic, regional, and religious identities. This hybrid naming practice signifies a form of cultural adaptation and integration where individuals maintain connections to both their linguistic heritage and religious affiliations. Thus, by categorizing names in this manner (See Table 2 & Figure 1), I aim to capture the rich tapestry of cultural and religious identities that inform naming practices within the community.

Table 2. Names collected from a Household survey of the past 70 years

Year	Total No. of names	No. of Telugu Names	No. of Urdu Names	No. of Urdu Names with Telugu Suffix or Prefix
1954-1963	68	36	8	24
1964-1973	59	22	13	24
1974-1983	99	30	41	28
1984-1993	82	21	40	21
1994-2003	120	29	65	26
2004-2013	114	23	75	16
2014-2023	58	10	42	6
Total	600	171	284	145

It is evident that the 600 names taken from the last seven decades demonstrate a steady growth of Urdu names coupled with a decrease in Telugu names and Urdu names with Telugu suffixes or prefixes, which makes a strong example of Islamization, which can be better visualized with a line chart diagram, converting the figures into percentages. Though the data makes a strong for Islamization over seven decades. However, when we look deeper into the data, we see a new trend followed by Dudekulas, which accommodates their traditional belief system by taking inspiration from the naming practice in Hinduism.

Figure 1. Dynamics of Naming among Dudekulas of Gundreddy Palle over the last 70 years in Percentages

5.4. New Naming Patterns

In this section, an effort has been made to shed light on the emerging naming practices among the Dudekulas, which creatively accommodate their traditional belief system with the help of Hindu naming conventions while adopting an Islamic name. This blending of traditions reflects the community’s negotiation between cultural heritage and religious identity, showcasing how they preserve syncretic practices even as they adapt to evolving religious influences.

During a household survey, Nagur bi (female, in her 30s) informed me that her two daughters were named Hasini and Nazeera. Intrigued, I inquired about the origins of these names, noting that Hasini is a Hindu name and Nazeera is Muslim. She explained that Nazeera’s original name was Ishita, a Hindu name meaning ‘divine power of Lord Ishwara’ but changed to Nazeera. When I asked her the reason for this change, she responded that:

If you ask me why, what can I say? She was not responding to that name. Additionally, she was crying when someone called that name. We (the couple) do not know what to do. We approached our (family) elders, then it was changed to Nazeera so that the name would begin with ‘Na’, in line with Narasimha Swamy, our household deity (*Narasinha svāmi pēru kalisi rāvālani “na” tō peṭṭukuṅṭām.*).

We can infer from her narrative that, although Ishita is traditionally a Hindu name, it was changed to Nazeera, which allowed them to integrate their household deity into their practices. This suggests that faith is not necessarily the primary determinant of naming choices; instead, a name’s functional role in accommodating cultural and familial needs takes precedence.

To delve deeper into this practice, I spoke with Narasimhulu, a Dudekula man in his mid-40s. He recounted an incident where a charitable trust led by a Dudekula person initially denied financial assistance to his daughter because her registered name, Lakshmi, was a Hindu name. However, the trust later agreed to help when it was revealed that she also had a Muslim name, Nasrin. Narasimhulu explained that all his daughters—Nazrin (birth name Lakshmi), Nasrin (registered name Lakshmi), and Nafrin (birth name Lakshmi)—were given both Hindu and Muslim names. His son, Sharif, was similarly registered under the name Narasimhulu. He said that his second daughter (Nasrin) wants to change her name officially in school records like her sisters but was persuaded by her teacher not to change it. He elaborated that while their ancestors originally had Islamic or Urdu names (*turukolla perlu*), the family shifted to naming their children after the deity Narasimha Swamy following a significant event known as the “tiger incident.” He emphasized that this practice is intentional (*Khalsālanē ga peṭṭindi*) and began recently after the construction of a new mosque. Prior to this, it was unknown; now, they intentionally incorporate the letter ‘Na’ without omitting it while giving Urdu names to identify as Muslims (*Na anē padam pōgaṭṭakunḍā, mana dānlō kalisē taṭṭu peṭṭinam*).

However, the response from younger generations differs significantly. Narasimhulu (a man in his mid-20s) explained that despite his registered name being Narasimhulu, he introduces himself as Sharif, a Muslim name, even in educational institutions where his registered name should be used. When asked, he recounts the “tiger incident.” He mentioned that maintaining the first letter of the household deity’s name is an age-old practice, and his paternal uncles’ children, named Nazir and Najeeb, continue this tradition. However, he expressed his desire to break this tradition and name his children without influence from their household deity.

We can detect this tendency by analyzing the naming patterns of the last two decades (see Table 3 and Figure 2). The categorization is intended to capture these patterns in the context of the impact of Islamic reformist organizations, which emphasize the use of Urdu names and the strategies adopted by the Dudekulas to accommodate their household deity while adhering to Islamic naming conventions. Sufi names are categorized separately because, with the rise of Islamic reformist organizations, Sufi names are no longer recognized as “Islamic” within mainstream Islam. This categorization aligns with the reformist movement’s emphasis on purely Urdu names, which reflect orthodox Islamic values. A blend of Urdu and Hindu names is categorized as Hybrid names. The timeframe of the last 20 years was chosen to examine the impact of significant events such as the construction of a new mosque, the introduction of a full-time Islamic religious preacher, and the influence of the Islamic reformist movement, which has been particularly prominent in the last ten years compared to the previous decade.

Table 3. Names collected from a Household survey of the past 20 years

Year	No. of Names	No. of Sufi name	No. of Urdu name without HHD letter	No. of Urdu name with HHD letter	No. of Hindu HHD name	Hybrid name
2003-2007	69	23	18	11	12	5
2008-2012	55	19	11	13	8	4
2013-2017	37	8	6	12	6	5
2018-2023	37	6	16	10	5	0
Total	198	56	51	46	31	14

Figure 2. Dynamics of Naming among Dudekulas of Gundreddy Palle over the last 20 years in Percentages

From the total of 198 names of the respondents born between 2003 and 2023, it is evident that the percentages of Sufi names and hybrid names are significantly decreasing, while the percentages of Urdu names with or without Hindu household deities are constantly going high. Meanwhile, the names of Hindu household deities are almost stable. However, this trend suggests not only the growing influence of Islamization but also a negotiation of Hindu and Islamic beliefs. The root of the idea is holding on to a first letter drawn from Hindu belief, in which the first letter of the name is usually determined by stars and constellations associated with the time of birth. Carrying root words from ancestral names is also prevalent among Hindus. It is also interesting to note that macro socio-cultural developments in India do not directly influence the naming patterns of the Dudekulas.

However, micro socio-cultural developments within the village are often shaped by these broader macro-level changes.

5.5. Towards Standardization of Names

When I was collecting household data from my participants, once I encountered an exciting interaction about the use of Hindu names in their daily lives. While I was asking Dastagiramma (female, 29) for the names of her children, a child on the street mentioned the name, Sunkulamma as her daughter’s name, but Dastagiramma corrected her. In response to that, the girl replied:

Girl: Isn’t your daughter’s name Sunkulamma? Why do you say Saleema?

Dastagiramma: You do not understand, little one; we must tell our names as they are on the Aadhar card.

Aadhar, a unique identification number assigned to individuals in India, is crucial for accessing government services. This necessity has influenced neonatal naming practices significantly. Traditionally, among Hindu families in the Rayalaseema region, names are not given to newborns immediately. Instead, the naming ceremony occurs after several months, typically around six months, based on factors such as *janma nakshatram* (birth star), Zodiac sign, the name of the year or month, household deity, caste deity, etc. Historically, this practice arose due to high infant mortality rates; only surviving infants were named.

Additionally, families used prefixes for names. For example, if a couple named their first child Narasimha, they would add the prefix *Pedda* (Elder) if they had another son, naming the second son *Chinna* (Younger) Narasimhulu. If they had a third son, Chinna Narasimhulu’s name would change to *Nadipi* (Middle) Narasimhulu, and the newborn would be named Chinna Narasimhulu. This pattern of *Pedda*, *Nadipi*, and *Chinna* prefixes was used for up to three children. If a fourth son were born, numerical prefixes would replace the traditional ones, such as First, Second, Third, and Fourth. This pattern applies to girl children too, the difference will be the couple will give the name Lakshmi, wife of Narasimha swamy.

Narasimhulu (a male in his mid-60s) shared his experiences with the Aadhar card and how it impacted his religious identity. In his (translated) words:

With the Aadhar cards, names became permanent; otherwise, we used to have household deity names. If we went to new places or met new people, we would identify ourselves as Sharif. Now, after Aadhar, true names have spread all over the country. Before the Aadhar cards, when we went to towns, we identified ourselves as Sharif and in villages as Narasimhulu. Now, whatever is mentioned on the Aadhar card is your name. You cannot alter it now. (Narasimhulu, a Dudekula male in his mid-60s)

Narasimhulu’s account highlights the significant impact of the Aadhar system on traditional naming practices and their fluidity. The standardization brought by the Aadhar card system aligns with administrative needs but clashes with traditional and cultural practices that value flexibility and context-specific identities. This shift underscores the tension between modernization and the preservation of cultural nuances.

Gender plays an important role in name-changing during marriages. Perayya (43, male) shared his perspective, stating that if there is a need to change the name, the names of the women always change during marriages. To explain this, he used the term “people from outside” (*Bayaṭa nuṅci vaccina vāḷḷu*), implying that women do not belong to their parental abode once married. The name of the woman changes to align with the groom’s name. In his case, his wife’s name was Dastagiramma before marriage, but it was changed to Kashamma to match with his name.

When I asked him who decided whether a name was in accordance with the groom’s name, he did not respond directly. Instead, he said, “We know it” (*Adi manaki ardhāṁ avutundi*), suggesting that the decision is based on a collective or intuitive understanding within the community. Additionally, the practice of changing names is influenced by a Hindu horoscope method called “*Peru Balam*”⁷, which is followed when a person does not know their Janma Nakshatram (birth star). This method helps in deciding a name that is believed to bring good fortune or compatibility within the marriage.

Even after sharing a common compound with Ramija (female, 35) and Perayya (male, 40) for more than a year and occasionally having food in their home, I only discovered that Ramija’s registered name was Peram Bi, which had been changed during her marriage, during my penultimate days in the field. This revelation came while conducting a household survey at their vegetable nursery, where Ramija’s mother was present. The conversation between us went like this:

Ramija’s mother: Ramija’s registered name is Peram Bi, the groom’s side changed it to Peram Bi during the marriage in anticipation of better fortune.

Me: Does the change in name lead to better fortunes in life?

[With a sarcastic smile on her face while looking at her husband]

Ramija: You should ask your uncle.

Ramija’s mother: Ramija was a good Muslim (turakam) name, yet it was changed to Peram Bi.

Me: Did anyone, including your mother, inform you about your name change during the marriage?

Ramija: [Nodding her head] Nobody told me about it. I was angry about it then and still am today. Even on the Ration card, Aadhar card, and everywhere else, it is written as Peram Bi. Now, wherever I go, I need to do that bloody (musti) signature.

Despite her official name being changed to Peram Bi, Ramija still identifies with her original name, highlighting the role of consent in one’s personal life with regard to name change. The change, intended to bring better fortune instead, brought slight frustration and a sense of disconnection from her sense of identity.

In the case of Mounica (a Dudekula woman with a Hindu name, in her mid-20s), when she married Sharif (male, 35), her name was changed in accordance with Islamic beliefs. However, this change was only for ritual purposes. In her in-laws’ home, she is still referred to as Mounica. When I asked her mother-in-law about the changed name, she

⁷ Matching horoscope of Bride and Groom before marriage.

did not know it and had to ask Mounica for it. Since Mounica was busy doing household chores inside the house and could not hear her mother-in-law, who was sitting with me on the porch, I did not insist on learning the new name. When I later spoke with her husband, I discovered that they had not changed her name in the official records because it would involve too much paperwork. This situation highlights the practical challenges and cultural nuances involved in name changes within the Dudekula community. While names may be altered for religious or cultural reasons, these changes are not always reflected in official documents, leading to a dual identity where individuals are known by different names in different contexts.

Ashok Kumar Mocherla (2020) explores a similar phenomenon in Dalits of coastal Andhra Pradesh, where people converted to Christianity and calls the result of the naming practices ‘Dual religious identities.’ The reasons for the dual name practices among Dalits are the growth of Christianity on the one hand, and the States’ institutionalized legal mechanism that deprives the Scheduled Caste status of Dalits who have converted to Christianity or Islam. The State and Church try to reimpose and restrict the people through various means. In the case of the State, it is official records, and in the case of the Church, it is marriage and death ceremonies. To negotiate with this, Dalit Christians formulated a strategy of Dual names. In the Public sphere, they identify themselves with Hindu names; in the private sphere, they identify themselves with Christian names. Dalit Christians’ ‘Christian names’ are popularly known as ‘Church names’ because they were given in Churches. He also describes how class affects dual religious identities.

However, in the case of the Dudekulas, choosing to have a registered Hindu name comes with significant socio-economic consequences. If they opt for a Hindu name, they must forgo the (OBC) reservation benefits the central government provides. This is because the Sachar Commission (2006) specifically recognizes Dudekula Muslims for these reservations. As a result, the interplay between state policies and religious identity creates a scenario where the State and Islam work together, albeit unintentionally, to impose homogenized identities on individuals. This issue is not as simple as it looks. In many parts of the state, the lack of knowledge of government officials regarding Dudekulas creates difficulties in getting OBC certificates, as many government officials do not issue OBC certificates if Dudekulas have Muslim names.⁸ These dynamics force the Dudekulas to navigate their identity in a way that aligns with official recognition and socio-economic advantages, highlighting the complex relationship between personal identity and institutional frameworks.

Conclusion

Based on the field data and discussions, we can conclude that naming practices are complex and often indirectly influenced by macro-level religious, cultural, and political factors while being directly shaped by micro-level ones. States’ bureaucratic requirements, such as the need for standardized documentation like the Aadhar card, have significantly impacted these fluid traditional naming practices. For administrative convenience, bureaucracy

⁸ <https://www.bbc.com/telugu/india-54896535>

enforces standardization, requiring names to be consistent across all official documents. While standardization helps in administrative efficiency and service delivery, it also leads to potentially diminishing rich cultural traditions. Balancing bureaucratic requirements with cultural practices remains a complex challenge for Dudekulas. It is essential to point out that Islamization informing a change in names among the Dudekulas implies a change in cultural practices rather than a shift in religious practices, which is similar to Rahman's (2013, p. 259) observation who argues that change in naming often reflects aspirations for status rather than religiosity. To second this, my findings also challenge the assumption that naming practices should be solely indicative of religious identity. When we see family as a unit, in some cases, Islamized names were not passed on to the subsequent generations. They again went back to the tradition of giving the name of their household deity or giving the name according to the first letter of their household deity. This suggests that individuals and communities may adopt new names to signal social mobility or to align with perceived socio-economic advantages rather than a genuine shift in religious or cultural practices. This nuanced understanding highlights the need to consider the broader socio-cultural and economic contexts when analyzing the implications of name changes within the framework of Islamization.

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